

Scale-up of the erythritol production technology – Process simulation and techno-economic analysis

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the scale-up of erythritol production from glycerol using the *Yarrowia lipolytica* strain MK1 is proposed. The experiments included increasing the scale from laboratory ($V_W = 0.002 \text{ m}^3$) to pilot plant ($V_P = 0.5 \text{ m}^3$). Only slight differences in the erythritol production rate were observed between the two culture variants. Erythritol concentration in the pilot plant experiment reached 180.3 kg/m^3 , with productivity $1.25 \text{ kg/m}^3 \cdot \text{h}$ and yield 0.533 kg/kg of the total amount of glycerol consumed. A model of an industrial installation for production of erythritol crystals, with the production rate of 1075 MT (Metric tone)/year, based on data derived from experimental work, was developed in SuperPro Designer V9.5 software. The potential of SuperPro Designer software was demonstrated in the framework of detailed analyses of cost-effectiveness and sensitivity for the production process. The industrial application of erythritol production from yeast is strongly dependent on the glycerol price and on the fermentation time. The process is based on cheap raw material, is fully scalable, and the collected data can serve as a basis for development of a production model. To our knowledge, this is the first report about scale-up of microbial erythritol production from glycerol and combined with the fact that the remaining biomass may be used as animal feed, makes the whole technology waste-free and economically viable.

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1. Introduction

Erythritol (1,2,3,4-butanetetrol) is a sugar alcohol, a member of the polyol family, forming white, odourless crystals. It occurs commonly in various fruits, such as melon, peach, pear, grapes, and also in fermented food products, such as wine, beer and soy sauce (Munro et al., 1998). Low caloric value (0.2 kcal/g) and sweetening properties corresponding to sucrose (70% of the sweetening power of sucrose) make it a useful and safe ingredient of low-calorie foods intended for persons suffering from diabetes or obesity (Goossens and Gonze, 1996). Toxicological studies demonstrated that erythritol is well tolerated and does not impose any side- or toxic effects (Bernt et al., 1996). Moreover, approximately 90% of erythritol ingested with foods does not undergo any biochemical modifications and is excreted in an unchanged form in urine, without

affecting blood sugar or insulin levels (Moon et al., 2010). Due to a specific molecular structure (presence of four hydroxyl residues), erythritol can also exert an antioxidative effect (den Hartog et al., 2010). The wide range of potential applications along with a number of interesting traits trigger increasing interest in this chemical compound from the food industry, as well as the cosmetic and pharmaceutical sectors.

Bioprocess scale-up is a fundamental factor of process development in the biotechnology industry. Large-scale and high-efficiency production of erythritol has not been established yet. However, the scale-up of the process is crucial for manufacturing commercial products in the industry. To date, the highest erythritol concentration using *Yarrowia lipolytica* yeast reached 201.2 kg/m^3 in 168 h of fed-batch cultures (Tomaszewska et al., 2014). The aim of process scale-up is to produce larger quantities with equivalent productivity and product quality. Process scale-up from laboratory to production scale remains a challenging task for microbial cell culture systems. Pilot plant data and operating know-how are used to improve the large-scale plant design (Fig. 1). The main issue that

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Fig. 1. Industrial process scale-up.

must be taken into consideration is oxygen transfer as a critical factor in the scale-up of the erythritol production process, because *Y. lipolytica* yeast is an aerobic microorganism (Barth and Gaillardin, 1997).

There are several methods of erythritol production via both chemical and biotechnological routes. One of the best known chemical processes relies on catalytic hydrolysis of starch dialdehyde to equimolar amounts of erythritol and ethylene glycol. However, due to a very low yield and relatively high costs of the substrate and the nickel catalyst, this method has not been implemented in industrial practice to date (Moon et al., 2010; Rice et al., 2019). Currently, it is commonly accepted that biotechnological processes exhibit great superiority with respect to erythritol production over chemical methods. The major microbiological players in biotechnological erythritol synthesis are osmophilic yeasts, e.g., *Moniliella pollinis*, *Trichosporonoides megachiliensis* and *Y. lipolytica* (Munro et al., 1998; Rzechonek et al., 2018), and several strains of lactic acid bacteria, e.g. *Oenococcus oeni*, *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* and *Lactobacillus sanfranciscensis* (Grembecka, 2015), showing corresponding capacity in synthesis of this compound.

The main substrate utilized by the abovementioned microbial strains is glucose, obtained through enzymatic hydrolysis of corn or wheat starch (Jeya et al., 2009; Park et al., 1998). As demonstrated by Jeya et al. (2009), in fed-batch cultures of *Pseudozyma tsukubaensis* strain grown in a medium with an average glucose content

of 400 kg/m³, the final erythritol titer amounted up to 245 kg/m³, showing great industrial potential of this process. However, considering the current unit cost of the main carbon source used in that process (367 €/MT of glucose (Koutinas et al., 2014)), the glucose-based erythritol production process may appear not economically feasible.

Residual glycerol, generated in high quantities as the principal by-product deriving from biodiesel production plants or oleochemical facilities (Rakicka et al., 2016; Papanikolaou and Aggelis, 2002), is characterized by much lower unit cost and equally good efficiency as a substrate in erythritol production. Great capacity for glycerol-to-erythritol conversion is a distinctive trait of the nonconventional yeast species *Y. lipolytica* (Celińska et al., 2016; Musiał et al., 2011; Tomaszewska et al., 2011; Yang et al., 2014). The viability of that process is comparable to those conducted with the abovementioned osmophilic yeasts cultured in glucose-based medium, especially when considering lower content of the main carbon source in the culturing medium (325 kg of glycerol/m³). Erythritol production using *Y. lipolytica* yeast and glycerol as a carbon source has been of high interest for a few years. Up to now, erythritol was produced in flask, batch, fed-batch and repeated batch cultures using different industrially relevant strains of *Y. lipolytica* with the concentration of polyol varying from 33.5 to 224 g/L (Rakicka et al., 2017; Tomaszewska et al., 2012). Moreover, the intensification of the product titer in comparison to simple batch culture was achieved through application of single-step continuous culture and two-stage continuous culture (Rakicka et al., 2016, 2017).

Unfortunately, all of the data available on erythritol biosynthesis using *Y. lipolytica* strains were acquired from cultures conducted on a laboratory scale (shake flasks or bioreactors) with the volume not exceeding 0.005 m³, which constitutes a serious limitation in performing a reliable techno-economic analysis of such technology. For all these reasons, the current study was divided into two principal stages. The first stage aimed at scaling up the erythritol production process using the *Y. lipolytica* strain MK1 from laboratory scale ($V_W = 0.002 \text{ m}^3$) to pilot plant-scale ($V_P = 0.5 \text{ m}^3$). The results obtained during these cultivations constituted a starting point for the second stage of this study, namely development of a model of an industrial installation for production of erythritol crystals, with the production rate of 1075 MT/year using SuperPro Designer V9.5 software. Based on this model, detailed analyses of cost-effectiveness and sensitivity for the production process were conducted.

Table 1

Comparison of geometrical parameters of the bioreactors used in this study.

Dimensions/operating conditions	Bioprocess scale	
	Laboratory bioreactor	Pilot plant bioreactor
Nominal vessel volume, V_N (m ³)	0.0066	1.5
Calculated working volume V_C (m ³)	0.002	0.488
Working volume used, V_W (m ³)	0.002	0.50
Impeller tip speed, ITS (m/s)	2.68	2.67
Agitation speed, N (rpm)	800	155
Number of impellers used	2	2
Impeller type	Rushton	Rushton
Liquid height, H_L (m)	0.113	0.718
Impeller diameter, D_I (m)	0.064	0.33
Reactor diameter, D_T Tank (m)	0.16	1.0
Reactor height, H_T (m)	0.34	2.0
H_T/D_T	2.16	2.0
D_I/D_T	0.40	0.33
H_L/D_T	0.706	0.718
Aeration rate (vvm)	0.3	0.3
Inoculum volume, V_X (m ³)	0.0002	0.05

2. Material and methods

2.1. Microorganism

Y. lipolytica strain MK1 was used in this study. The strain was isolated from the *Y. lipolytica* strain Wratislavia K1 after its exposure to UV irradiation (Mirończuk et al., 2015a). The strain was deposited in the culture collection of the Department of Biotechnology and Food Microbiology, at Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Science.

2.2. Substrate

The main substrate used in the culture media composition was residual glycerol from Orlen Południe Group Refinery (Poland). The substrate contained 80% (w/w) glycerol, 9% (w/w) water, 5% (w/w) NaCl and approximately 6% (w/w) organic matter (matter organic non-glycerol, MONG).

Fig. 2. Erythritol biosynthesis from residual glycerol by *Y. lipolytica* MK-1 strain in fed-batch cultures conducted in the laboratory-scale bioreactor ($V_W = 0.002 \text{ m}^3$) (2a) and the pilot plant bioreactor ($V_P = 0.5 \text{ m}^3$) (2b). \blacktriangle - mannitol, \bullet - erythritol, \blacksquare - glycerol, \blacktriangledown - α -Ketoglutaric acid, \blacklozenge - arabinol, \circ - biomass.

2.3. Culture media

Pre-cultures were prepared in shake flasks in a medium of the following composition: residual glycerol 50 g/L; yeast extract 3 g/L; bacteriological peptone 3 g/L. Production cultures, in both laboratory scale ($V_W = 0.002 \text{ m}^3$) and pilot plant scale ($V_P = 0.5 \text{ m}^3$), were conducted in a production medium containing: residual glycerol 300 (100 + 200) g/L; yeast extract 1 g/L, KH_2PO_4 0.25 g/L, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ 4.6 g/L, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.3 g/L and tap water up to 1 L (Rywińska et al., 2015). pH of both media was adjusted to 3.0. The production medium was not thermally sterilized before cultivations. Preliminary cultivations in laboratory-scale bioreactors indicated that the applied low pH provided sufficient protection against potential contamination.

2.4. Bioreactors and scale-up

Scale-up of the bioprocesses requires preservation of specific conditions related to the bioreactor's geometry, and the structure of individual subunits responsible for example mixing, being particularly important in aerobic cultures, is an absolute prerequisite in a process of technology scale-up (Burke, 2008). The present obtained results of the laboratory-scale cultivations conducted in 0.002 m^3 of production medium (Biostat Bplus, Sartorius Stedim, Germany) constituted the starting point in the process of scaling up of the erythritol production. Considering that this study ultimately aims at developing a model of erythritol synthesis on the commercial scale, it was decided to apply a relatively high scale factor (SF) of 250. Thus, the medium volume in the subsequent vessel should be 0.5 m^3 . For the pilot plant-scale cultivations, a bioreactor of the nominal vessel volume of 1.5 m^3 (Bioflo IF-1500, New Brunswick

Scientific, USA) was used. The geometrical parameters of the pilot plant bioreactor corresponded to those characterizing the laboratory-scale vessels (Table 1).

Both bioreactors were equipped with the same type of mechanical impeller (two Rushton turbines), and the ratio between the height and the diameter of the vessels (H_T/D_T) was corresponding. The actual working volume of the culture medium that should be applied to the production cultures was calculated by allowing for the diameters of both culturing vessels (D_{T1} , D_{T2}) and the working volume of the medium applied in the laboratory-scale cultivations (Eq. (1)) (Ju and Chase, 1992):

$$\frac{D_{T2}}{D_{T1}} = \left(\frac{V_{W2}}{V_{W1}} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (1)$$

where, D_{T1} = diameter of the laboratory-scale bioreactor (m), D_{T2} = diameter of the pilot plant-scale bioreactor (m), V_{W1} = working volume of the culture medium in the laboratory-scale bioreactor (m^3), V_{W2} = working volume of the culture medium in the pilot plant-scale bioreactor (m^3).

According to these calculations, to ideally mimic the geometrical similarity between the two bioreactors, $0.488 m^3$ of the culture medium should be applied in the pilot plant-scale vessel. The calculated value differed only slightly from the initial presumption; thus, the value was rounded up to $0.5 m^3$, which allowed the established scale factor to be maintained ($SF = 250$). This rounding up did not significantly influence the ratio between the actual, measured height of the liquid column in the bioreactors and their diameters (H_T/D_T) (Table 1). In order to maintain similar hydrodynamic conditions between the two bioreactor cultures, impeller tip speed (ITS) determined for the laboratory-scale bioreactor (Eq. (2)) (Ju and Chase, 1992) was used to rescale and determine agitation speed in the pilot-plant bioreactor (Table 1).

$$ITS = \frac{\pi N D_I}{60} \quad (2)$$

where: N = agitation speed (rpm), D_I = impeller diameter (m).

2.5. Culture conditions

Pre-cultures for the first step of the laboratory-scale bioreactor cultivations ($0.002 m^3$) were prepared in shake flasks with the total volume of 250 ml and the culture medium volume of 50 mL, in an Elpan rotary shaker (Poland) at $30^\circ C$ and 140 rpm, for 48 h. The bioreactors were inoculated at 10% (w/v) with the pre-cultures. In the case of the pilot plant-scale bioreactor cultures ($0.5 m^3$), propagation of pre-cultures was conducted in two subsequent

Table 2
Parameters characterizing bioconversion of raw glycerol to erythritol by *Y. lipolytica* Wratslavia K1 in the two different scales.

Parameter	Bioprocess scale	
	Laboratory bioreactor $V_W = 0.002 m^3$	Pilot plant bioreactor $V_P = 0.5 m^3$
Time (h)	146.0	144.0
Erythritol (kg/m^3)	165.0	180.3
Mannitol (kg/m^3)	6.90	7.063
α -Ketoglutaric acid (kg/m^3)	6.3	6.76
Arabitol (kg/m^3)	3.0	2.8
Biomass (kg/m^3)	27.0	24.41
Residual glycerol (kg/m^3)	0.0	0.0
Y_{ERY} (kg/kg)	0.525	0.533
Q_{ERY} ($kg/m^3 \cdot h$)	1.13	1.25
q_{ERY} ($kg/kg \cdot h$)	0.042	0.051

bioreactors containing respectively 0.005 and $0.05 m^3$ of the production medium. These pre-cultures were also grown for 48 h. Each of the bioreactors was inoculated at 10% (w/v) with the culture from the preceding step.

The pilot plant-scale bioreactor cultures were conducted in a fed-batch mode. The initial glycerol concentration in the production medium was approximately 100 g/L. The next portions of the substrate were added to reach the final glycerol concentration of 300 g/L. The feeds were executed not earlier than after 24 h of culturing. pH was maintained through automatic addition of 20% (w/w) NaOH solution. Aeration was delivered by a traditional sparger located below the lowest Rushton turbine of the impeller. Air flow was maintained at the level of 0.3 vvm throughout the cultures, and corrected upon each feeding execution to the desired level. The cultures were protected against excessive foaming with an anti-foam agent, Acepol (Emerald Foam Control, USA).

2.6. Analytical techniques

Dry biomass concentration was determined through a standard gravimetric method. Briefly, samples (10 mL) withdrawn from the cultures were centrifuged (10 min; $4^\circ C$; 4600 g), then the biomass was harvested by filtration through $0.45 \mu m$ pore cellulose membranes and washed twice with distilled water. The dry biomass was determined gravimetrically after drying at $105^\circ C$.

The concentrations of glycerol, erythritol, arabitol and mannitol in the supernatant were determined by high-performance liquid chromatography. Samples were first centrifuged (5 min; $4^\circ C$; 12,000 g; Multifuge 3SR, Germany), filtered through a $0.22 \mu m$ membrane filter (Millex-GS, Millipore, USA), and then analyzed using an HPLC system, Agilent Technologies 1200 series. The chromatograph was equipped with a HyperRez Carbohydrate H + Column (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA), and refractive index and DAD detectors. Analyses were performed isocratically, at a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min, at a constant temperature of $65^\circ C$. Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) (25 mM) was used as the mobile phase. External standards were applied for identification and quantification of peak areas.

2.7. Calculation of fermentation parameters

The yield of erythritol production from glycerol (Y_{ERY}), expressed in kg/kg , was calculated using Equation (3) (Rywińska et al., 2015):

$$Y_{ERY} = \frac{P}{S} \quad (3)$$

The volumetric production rate of erythritol (Q_{ERY}), expressed in $kg/m^3 \cdot h$, was calculated using Equation (4) (Rywińska et al., 2015):

$$Q_{ERY} = \frac{P}{t} \quad (4)$$

The specific production rate of erythritol (q_{ERY}), expressed in $kg/kg \cdot h$, was calculated using Equation (5) (Rywińska et al., 2015):

$$q_{ERY} = \frac{Q_{ERY}}{X} \quad (5)$$

In all these equations, P denotes erythritol concentration in the culture broth at the end of the cultivations (kg/m^3), S indicates the total amount of glycerol consumed (kg/m^3), t denotes duration of the fermentation process (h), and X represents biomass concentration at time t (kg/m^3).

Table 3
Bulk materials used in scale-up of the erythritol production technology.

Material	MT/yr	MT/batch	MT/MT·MP
Antifoam	1	0.04	0.00
Air	24,533	791.38	24.32
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	2	0.06	0.00
Glycerol 80%	3017	97.33	2.99
HCl (5% w/w)	61	1.96	0.06
KH ₂ PO ₄	0	0.00	0.00
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0	0.00	0.00
Mineral medium	33	1.07	0.03
NaCl (2 M)	1717	55.39	1.70
NaOH (20% w/w)	39	1.24	0.04
NaOH (4% w/w)	4876	157.28	4.83
Water	48,722	1571.66	48.30
Yeast extract	7	0.22	0.01
TOTAL	83,007	2677.64	82.28

MT – metric tone, yr – year, MP – main product.

2.8. Model development and techno-economic assessment

Based on the results from the pilot plant-scale fed-batch cultivations and the data on erythritol purification presented by Rakicka et al. (2016), a model of industrial installation for commercial production of erythritol was developed using SuperPro Designer V9.5 software (Intelligen, Massachusetts, USA). The end product was formulated as erythritol crystals with erythritol content of at least 99.5% (w/w). Production rate of the installation was 1075 MT/

year, yielding 1000 tonnes of pure erythritol/year. According to the model, the installation was planned to work over 24 h a day, for 350 days a year. The batch throughput per year is 31 and duration for each batch is 266.18 h. The remaining days were planned for service and conservation works. Estimations on the capital expense (CAPEX) and the operational expense (OPEX) were prepared for the model, along with cost effectiveness and sensitivity analyses (Ulrich and Vasudevan, 2004).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Yeast biomass during scale-up of the erythritol biosynthesis process

In order to assess the process scalability, the two cultivation variants – laboratory-scale bioreactor ($V_W = 0.002 \text{ m}^3$) and pilot plant-scale bioreactor ($V_P = 0.5 \text{ m}^3$) – were compared with respect to the kinetics of *Y. lipolytica* biomass propagation. The pilot plant-scale culture was preceded by two stages of inoculum propagation in the production medium. According to the literature data, such an approach allows one to significantly reduce the stage of the cell adaptation in the actual production culture (Lincoln, 1960; Stanbury et al., 1995). The results presented in Fig. 2a and b clearly demonstrate that the growth kinetics was significantly different between the two cultivation variants. In the laboratory-scale bioreactor, the maximal biomass concentration of 27 g/L was reached at 24 h of culturing, resulting in the biomass volumetric

Fig. 3. Process flow diagram for the erythritol production process from inoculation to separation of product.

productivity of 1.125 g/L·h within the first 24 h. Corresponding results were obtained with the *Y. lipolytica* strain Wratislavia K1 grown in fed-batch cultures, fed with PM4 medium, with the total glycerol concentration reaching 325 g/L (Tomaszewska et al., 2014).

In contrast, the initial volumetric productivity of the yeast biomass in the pilot plant cultures was over two-fold lower (0.512 g/L·h), as the biomass concentration reached 21 g/L after 41 h. Importantly, in the pilot plant cultures the biomass growth continued until 93 h, reaching a peak value of 25.3 g/L at this time-point – a similar level to that observed for the laboratory-scale cultivations. Probably, the observed differences in the biomass growth kinetics could be attributed to a different mode of inocula preparation for the two culture variants. For the pilot plant cultures, subsequent stages of the pre-culture propagation involved passages through 0.005 followed by 0.05 m³ volumes of the production medium, lacking bacteriological peptone, and with only 1 g/L of yeast extract. By contrast, laboratory-scale bioreactors were inoculated at 10% with the pre-cultures grown in the pre-culture medium containing three-fold higher yeast extract concentration (3 g/L) and including bacteriological peptone at 3 g/L. Yeast extract contains approximately 11.9% nitrogen and 39.13% carbon. Elementary composition of bacteriological peptone is even richer in nitrogen and carbon atoms, with the percentage content being up to 15.24% and 43.61%, for each element respectively. Thus, both of the compounds constitute not only a rich source of nitrogen, but also easily accessible carbon, as previously demonstrated for *Y. lipolytica* (Celińska et al., 2016). Both media constituents provide substantial amounts of vitamins and minerals playing a crucial in *Y. lipolytica* growth (Tomaszewska et al., 2011). It is worth noting that scaling up the process did not negatively affect biomass formation. Aerobe *Y. lipolytica* grew well in large-scale cultivation and oxygen transfer was sufficient.

3.2. Erythritol production in bioreactor scale-up process

The intensity of erythritol synthesis increased substantially

followed by feeding execution (Fig. 2a and b). The increase in glycerol concentration imposed by the feed triggered rise in osmotic pressure, which in turn is known to induce erythrose reductase activity, being responsible for conversion of erythrose to erythritol (Mirończuk et al., 2015b; Park et al., 2011; Yang et al., 2014). Only slight differences in the erythritol production rate were observed between the two culture variants. While in the laboratory-scale bioreactor, erythritol concentration increased linearly between 24 and 144 h of culture, with the slope value, calculated through linear regression analysis, of 1.29 ($R^2 = 0.99$), in the pilot plant-scale bioreactor, the slope value, calculated with the data collected between 47 and 144 h, was 1.83 ($R^2 = 0.94$). The remaining kinetic parameters related to the culture productivity and bioconversion yield were all at a comparable level (Table 2). Both cultures lasted for nearly 150 h, and terminated upon full consumption of glycerol. Concomitantly, the final profile of the major by-products, which were arabitol, mannitol and α -Ketoglutaric acid, was qualitatively and quantitatively highly similar for both culture variants. Erythritol concentration obtained in the present study is close to the value noted by Rakicka et al. (2017) for the *Y. lipolytica* strain Wratislavia K1 growing on crude and pure glycerol in two-stage culture and only slightly lower than the concentration of erythritol obtained by Yang et al. (2014) in fed-batch culture on glycerol by *Y. lipolytica* CICC 1675.

3.3. Simulation of erythritol production process Table 3

The process flow diagrams, which are presented in Figs. 3 and 4, were created and then validated using SuperPro Designer V9.5 software. The process flow diagrams correspond to the production of erythritol in fed-batch mode using *Yarrowia* yeast and the purification procedure is based on the experimental results presented by Rakicka et al. (2016). In Supplementary data 1, the summary of detailed properties of streams during scale-up of the erythritol production technology are presented. Propagation of inocula is performed through stages 1-1 to 1-4 (Fig. 3). Water, glycerol,

Fig. 4. Process flow diagram of erythritol purification.

Table 4

The detailed consumption of individual materials per section of the scale-up of the erythritol production technology.

Procedure	% Total	MT/yr	MT/batch
Antifoam			
BT-1	94.48	1	0.04
I-1	0.00	0	0.00
I-2	0.01	0	0.00
I-3	0.26	0	0.00
I-4	5.24	0	0.00
Air			
KP-1	90.47	22,194	715.95
P-0003	9.53	2338	75.43
TOTAL	100.00	24,533	791.38
(NH₄)₂SO₄			
I-1	0.01	0	0.00
I-2	0.24	0	0.00
I-3	4.75	0	0.00
I-4	95.00	2	0.05
TOTAL	100.00	2	0.06
Glycerol			
Z-M-1	98.44	2970	95.82
I-1	0.00	0	0.00
I-2	0.00	0	0.00
I-3	0.07	2	0.07
I-4	1.48	45	1.44
TOTAL	100.00	3017	97.33
HCl (5% w/w)			
P-0010	100.00	61	1.96
TOTAL	100.00	61	1.96
KH₂PO₄			
I-1	0.01	0	0.00
I-2	0.24	0	0.00
I-3	4.75	0	0.00
I-4	95.00	0	0.00
TOTAL	100.00	0	0.00
MgSO₄ · 7H₂O			
I-1	0.01	0	0.00
I-2	0.24	0	0.00
I-3	4.75	0	0.00
I-4	95.00	0	0.00
TOTAL	100.00	0	0.00
Mineral medium			
BT-1	100.00	33	1.07
TOTAL	100.00	33	1.07
NaCl (2M)			
P-0012	100.00	1717	55.39
TOTAL	100.00	1717	55.39
NaOH (20% w/w)			
F-1	99.18	38	1.23
I-1	0.00	0	0.00
I-2	0.00	0	0.00
I-3	0.04	0	0.00
I-4	0.78	0	0.01
TOTAL	100.00	39	1.24
NaOH (4% w/w)			
P-0011	100.00	4876	157.28
TOTAL	100.00	4876	157.28
Water			
BT-1	13.96	6803	219.45
F-1	2.78	1355	43.70
I-1	0.00	0	0.00
I-2	0.01	4	0.13
I-3	0.08	39	1.25
I-4	0.97	473	15.26
W-1	0.01	4	0.12
Z-M-3	0.78	378	12.18
IE-1	27.14	13,222	426.53
IE-2	12.77	6222	200.71
IE-3	6.05	2948	95.10
IE-4	2.89	1409	45.46
IE-5	1.40	681	21.96
P-0010	4.26	2076	66.95
P-0011	9.05	4409	142.23
P-0012	3.26	1589	51.25
P-0013	11.24	5475	176.63
P-0002	3.36	1635	52.76

Table 4 (continued)

Procedure	% Total	MT/yr	MT/batch
TOTAL	100.00	48,722	1571.66
Yeast extract			
BT-1	94.48	6	0.21
I-1	0.00	0	0.00
I-2	0.01	0	0.00
I-3	0.26	0	0.00
I-4	5.25	0	0.01
TOTAL	100.00	7	0.22

MT – metric tone, yr-year.

ammonium sulfate, potassium dihydrogen phosphate, mineral medium, yeast extract and antifoam are fed to blending tank BT-1, which operates in batch mode. All process streams characterized in [Supp. Fig. S1](#) work at 25 °C under pressure 1.0133 bar, except the Vent-3 stream, which operates at 20 °C and the same pressure as the others. The stream from tank BT-1, with total mass flow of all raw materials equal to 211.88 MT/batch (S-1-Glycerol batch, S-3-Mmed, S-4-YE, S-5-AF, S-6-Water) and inocula (FR-1), with mass flow equal to 12,086 kg/batch, are fed to the industrial fermenter F-1 ([Fig. 3](#), [Supp. Fig. S1](#)). The fermentation lasts for 140 h and takes place in fed-batch mode. The amount of glycerol added is 62.05 MT/batch ([Supp. 1](#)). Erythritol concentration in the fed-batch mode reached 180.3 kg/m³, with productivity 1.25 kg/m³·h and yield 0.533 kg/kg of the total amount of glycerol consumed. The overall glycerol to erythritol conversion yield was 0.42 g/g. The yeast biomass (32.65 MT/batch) produced as a byproduct is separated from fermentation liquid via centrifugation (W-1) and raw erythritol liquid (240.46 MT/batch) is obtained (Z-M-4) ([Fig. 3](#), [Supp. Fig. S1](#)). As shown in [Fig. 3](#), biomass was partially recirculated or dried by drum drying (P-004). In [Fig. 4](#) the proposed process flow diagram of the purification of raw erythritol broth is presented. The process is carried out as an independently cycling procedure, regardless of the main schedule. Purification of raw erythritol is first conducted via ion exclusion (IE-1 to IE-5 columns) ([Fig. 4](#)). The erythritol stream after this stage is equal to 555.79 MT/batch ([Supp. Fig. S1](#)). Total mass flows of Recycle-5, which might be recirculated to the purification process or utilized, is 9.99 MT/batch and Waste-1A is 503.64 MT/batch ([Supp. Fig. S1](#)). Next, the erythritol stream is purified by ion exchange (P-001 to P-0012) and 826.41 MT/batch of erythritol is obtained ([Fig. 4](#), [Supp. Fig. S1](#)). The Waste-1B stream generated at this stage contains 414.00 MT/batch of flow mass. After discoloration on an activated carbon column, evaporation and crystallization are performed ([Fig. 4](#)). Flow mass of water (Water vapor-1a) generated in these procedures is equal to 631.81 MT/batch ([Supp. Fig. S1](#)). Finally, 194.02 MT/batch of erythritol is directed to rotary vacuum filtration and next to rotary drying ([Fig. 4](#)). The Waste-1C stream generated at this stage is 135.89 MT/batch and the Water vapor-1b stream is 158.35 MT/batch ([Supp. Fig. S1](#)). At the end of the process 34.333 MT/batch of erythritol crystals is generated ([Supp. Fig. S1](#)).

The cost of total investment is more than €16 M and the material costs are almost €1500 ([Supp. 2](#)). In [Table 3](#) the individual consumption of materials used in the entire process is presented. The total consumption of all materials per year is more than €86 MT ([Table 3](#)). The water and air consumption in the presented technology is 1571.66 and 791.38 MT/batch, respectively ([Table 3](#)). The most applied materials in the process are glycerol with 97.33 MT/batch, 2 M NaCl with 55.39 MT/batch and 4% (w/w) NaOH with 157.28 MT/batch ([Table 3](#)). In [Table 4](#), the detailed consumption of the individual raw materials and utilities consumption in all streams during the process is determined. Antifoam is used in blending tank BT-1 and in small quantities during production of inocula (I-2, I-3, I-4). Air is necessary for the aerobic yeast growth

Fig. 5. Relationship between rankings of different variables to the price of erythritol.

process and its consumption is equal to 791.38 MT/batch. Among loose materials, the minimal medium is used in the highest amount in stream BT-1 (Table 4). The highest quantity of sodium base and sodium chloride are used in streams P-0011 and P-0012, respectively, during ion exchange (Table 4). The most water consuming stream is IE-1 during preparation of inocula (Table 4). Moreover, Supplementary material 3 contains detailed information about components consumed and produced in all streams such as carbon dioxide, erythritol crystals, raw erythritol, mannitol, arabitol and α -Ketoglutaric acid. Production rate of the installation is 1075 MT/year, yielding 1000 tonnes of pure erythritol/year. According to the model, the installation was planned to work over 24 h a day, for 350 days a year. The batch throughput per year is 31 and duration for each batch is 266.18 h. The net present value (NPV) for the presented installation is greater than zero (€6 M), which means the project may be accepted.

3.4. Sensitivity analysis

The impact of several variables such as time of fermentation,

centrifugation, drying and variables related to the cost of materials on the costs of production erythritol crystals was determined in the sensitivity analysis (Figs. 5 and 6). As can be seen from Figs. 5 and 6 the costs of substrate used in the presented technology (glycerol) are crucial for cost-competitive production of erythritol. The glycerol market size was over USD 2 billion in 2017 and industry expects consumption of over 4 million tonnes by 2024 (<https://www.gminsights.com/industry-analysis/glycerol-market-size>). Glycerol is mainly generated from biodiesel, thereby making it a renewable and clean-burning fuel which can be used for industrial purposes. The price of glycerol on the USA market in 2018 was 47 c/lb for a technical product with purity of 95%, and 18 c/lb for technical glycerol with 80% purity (<http://www.hbint.com/datas/media/590204fd077a6e381ef1a252/sample-quarterly-glycerine.pdf>). Production of erythritol using yeast is also strongly dependent on fermentation time (Figs. 5 and 6). This is undoubtedly the longest stage of the process, in which the highest product titer and productivity should be achieved. Other cultivation systems such as continuous culture or repeated batch-culture in which productivity and yield of erythritol were also very satisfactory should be taken

Fig. 6. Contribution to the price of erythritol of different variables based on variance-based sensitivity analysis.

Fig. 7. Tornado diagram for erythritol production profitability.

into consideration (Mirończuk et al., 2015a; Rakicka et al., 2016). The fast adaptation of yeast and the innovative fermenter designs in which the fermentation time will be shortened are needed in order to reduce the cost of the final product. Such changes are necessary for commercial application of the presented technology of erythritol production. The tornado plot presented in Fig. 7 compares the relative importance of several variables for price of erythritol crystals. As can be seen from this diagram the sensitive variable – the product cost – is strongly correlated with the price of substrate and fermentation time (Fig. 7). Koutinas et al. (2014) came to a similar conclusion when they analyzed microbial oil production, which is also strongly dependent on the feedstock used and on the fermentation stage.

Summing up, it can be concluded that the presented process is fully scalable, and the collected data can serve as a basis for development of a production model. The technology uses an industrially relevant strain of *Y. lipolytica* and the cheap renewable material glycerol as a carbon source. Moreover, the process does not require sterilization due to the low pH of the medium. Biosynthesis of erythritol was performed in non-aseptic conditions, which leads to lower energy consumption and reduces the cost of the entire technology (data not shown). In this article a study of the economics of erythritol production using yeast is presented. The price of glycerol and fermentation time have the main impacts on the cost of the final product.

4. Conclusions

In the present study, erythritol production technology scale-up based on glycerol using a *Y. lipolytica* yeast strain is proposed. To our knowledge, this is the first report about a scaled up erythritol production process. Increasing the scale of production did not negatively affect the parameters of erythritol biosynthesis. First, the product titer increases significantly over batch or fed-batch culture, and second, the productivity and yield reached a higher, very satisfactory rate. Erythritol production in the pilot plant experiment reached 180.3 kg/m³, with productivity 1.25 kg/m³·h and yield 0.533 kg/kg of the total amount of glycerol consumed. This study showed a great industrial potential of the yeast strain of *Y. lipolytica* and is a starting point for development of a production model in industry. The proposed industrial technology is able to produce erythritol crystals, with the production rate of 1075 MT/year. The economic evaluation of current technologies that focus on microbial erythritol production is essential in order to assess the potential for commercialization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Magdalena Rakicka-Pustułka: Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Aleksandra M. Mirończuk:** Methodology, Investigation. **Ewelina Celińska:** Methodology, Writing - original draft. **Wojciech Białas:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing - original draft. **Waldemar Rymowicz:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Project administration.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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